

A GENERIC FRAMEWORK FOR THERMO-MECHANICAL CREEP OF THERMOPLASTIC MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Thermoplastic composites are increasingly used as load carrying materials and are replacing traditional materials. Creep response of a material is an important design factor, which defines the design life of a product. Thus, characterization and predictability of the thermo-mechanical creep response is critical for the associated product design, *e.g.*, thermoplastic composite pipes. The creep response of high-density polyethylene material is considered in the current study. Thermo-mechanical creep material model is calibrated using Digimat – a material modelling software, and follows the usual creep framework, *e.g.*, Prony series, time-temperature superposition and Williams-Landel-Ferry shift function. The original contribution is towards establishing a generic framework to identify the creep calibration parameters unequivocally. The generic methodology developed herein can be used for any thermoplastic materials and provides a systematic, and time-efficient approach for the material calibration.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic composites are increasingly used as load carrying materials and are replacing traditional materials. For example, thermoplastic composite pipes (TCPs) offer unique value propositions for metal dominated offshore oil & gas domain. The fully-bonded TCPs offered by Airborne Oil & Gas are enabling for deeper water exploration, production and intervention, and put an end to corrosion.

Creep response of a material is an important design factor, which defines the design life of a product. Thus, characterization and predictability of the thermo-mechanical creep response is critical for the associated product design. The TCPs are subjected to various temperatures and loading conditions during their design life. The TCPs consist of glass or carbon fibre reinforcements completely embedded within a thermoplastic material, *e.g.*, high-density polyethylene (HDPE), Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), etc.

The thermo-mechanical creep response of the HDPE material is considered in the current study. Thermo-mechanical creep material model is calibrated using Digimat – a material modelling software, and follows the usual creep framework, *e.g.*, Prony series, time-temperature superposition and Williams-Landel-Ferry shift function. The theoretical framework of the thermo-mechanical creep is reviewed in Section 2.

In Section 3, a generic framework is developed to identify the creep calibration parameters unequivocally following a systematic methodology. The methodology developed herein can be used for any thermoplastic materials and provides a systematic, and time-efficient approach for the thermo-mechanical creep calibration. In Section 4, an application case study is given for the thermoplastic composite consisting of HDPE reinforced with continuous glass-fibers. The creep response of the HDPE material is first calibrated for various temperatures and loading conditions using Digimat. The thermo-mechanical creep response relies on the Prony-series and a master curve based on the time-temperature superposition as outlined in Section 3. The summary and conclusions of the present study are given in Section 5.

2 THERMO-MECHANICAL CREEP OF POLYMERS

Polymeric materials exhibit time-dependent viscoelastic behavior, *i.e.*, at a given load the stress and strain change over time. Creep governs the deformation of a material subjected to a sustained applied stress. The creep phenomenon is introduced in Section 2.1 and the constitutive law of viscoelasticity is reviewed in Section 2.2. Since the response is time-dependent, a polymeric material will deform under shorter or longer time scales as it would deform under higher or lower temperatures, respectively. This is characteristic of the time-temperature superposition principle, which implies the equivalence among the time and the temperature of viscoelastic polymers, and is given in Section 2.3.

2.1 Creep

Creep governs the deformation of a material subjected to a sustained applied stress. It is used to characterize the long-term behavior of the polymers. The resulting strain from the creep is usually recorded as a function of the time, which evolves through three different stages; the primary, secondary and tertiary creep, and are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the primary, secondary and tertiary creep strains as function of the logarithmic time

During the primary or transient creep, the strain rate decreases with the time. This stage is followed by a secondary steady-state creep stage where the strain rate remains constant. Finally, the strain rate increases until failure in the tertiary creep stage, see Figure 1. In Figure 2, the primary and secondary creep stages are shown for different stress levels. A linear viscoelastic behavior is characterized by creep strains that remain proportional to the applied stresses. This behavior is illustrated in Figure 2 and will further be considered in this paper. If the creep strains are not proportional to the applied stresses, the response is characterized by a nonlinear viscoelastic or viscoplastic behavior. Note that a viscoelastic behavior is observed when the stress is applied below the yield stress $\sigma < \sigma_y$. This behavior is characterized with the recovery of the deformation when the applied stress is released. A viscoplastic behavior is observed when the applied stress is above the yield stress $\sigma > \sigma_y$. This behavior yields a permanent deformation that remains upon the released stress. In this paper, we consider that the time-dependent deformation in the polymeric material is largely governed by the viscoelasticity.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of linear viscoelasticity at different stress levels $\sigma_1 < \sigma_2 < \sigma_3$

2.2 Constitutive law for viscoelasticity

The viscoelastic behavior of the thermoplastic material can be represented by different models, amongst which is the Prony series modeled in Digimat [1, 2] as:

$$E(t) = E^0 \left[1 - \sum_{i=1}^n w_i (1 - e^{-t/\tau_i}) \right] \quad (1)$$

where $E^0 = E(t = 0)$ is the initial elastic modulus and w_i and τ_i are the weight and time respectively of the relaxation i . It can be observed that Equation (1) contains two terms. The first term corresponds to the time-independent instantaneous modulus, whereas the second term involves a time-dependency characteristic of the viscoelastic behavior.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of the relaxation modulus characterized by a Prony series

The polymer relaxation described by a number of Prony series terms is schematically represented in Figure 3. At $t = 0$, the instantaneous elastic modulus E^0 corresponds to the modulus of the material loaded at an infinite strain rate. Each weight w_i is a measure of the sensitivity of the material to a given strain rate and hence to the stiffness variation around the corresponding relaxation time. A small weight associated to a relaxation time implies a limited variation of the stiffness around that relaxation time, whereas a large weight associated to a relaxation time implies a large variation of the stiffness around that relaxation time. At $t = \infty$, the long-term elastic modulus E^∞ corresponds to the modulus of the material loaded at a quasi-static strain rate:

$$E^\infty = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} E(t) = E^0 \left[1 - \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \right] \quad (2)$$

Resulting from Equation (1), four parameters are needed to describe the viscoelastic behavior of a polymer. These parameters are the time-independent instantaneous modulus E^0 on the one hand and the parameters of the Prony series on the other hand, and are reviewed in Sections 3.1 and 3.2, respectively. The parameters of the Prony series consist of n -number of Prony series terms, their respective relaxation times τ_i and weights w_i .

2.3 Time-temperature superposition

As the elastic modulus of a viscoelastic material increases with an increasing strain rate, so does the elastic modulus decreases with increasing temperature. This is known as the time-temperature superposition principle and is illustrated in Figure 4. The time-temperature superposition principle implies the equivalence among the time and the temperature of viscoelastic polymers. Thence, the time needed for a material to relax is smaller at higher temperature. Conversely, the time needed for a material to relax is higher at smaller temperature. Therefore, measurements along the same time range at different constant temperatures can be used to construct a master curve at a reference temperature T_{ref} .

Figure 4: Schematic representation of the construction of the master curve at $T_{ref} = T_0$ based on the time-temperature superposition principle

The master curve is constructed by shifting the other curves with respect to the time. Hereby, it predicts the polymer relaxation over a larger time range than would experimentally be possible. The horizontal shift of the viscoelastic relaxation can be described by the Williams-Landel-Ferry (WLF) shift function, the shift factor a_T being expressed as:

$$\log a_T = -\frac{C_1(T-T_{ref})}{C_2+(T-T_{ref})} \quad (3)$$

where T_{ref} denotes the reference temperature and C_1 and C_2 are constants. Hence, resulting from Equation (3), two parameters are needed to define the shift function. These parameters are the unknown constants C_1 and C_2 , and are reviewed in Section 3.4.

3 IDENTIFICATION OF THERMO-MECHANICAL CREEP PARAMETERS

The thermo-mechanical creep behavior of polymers is calibrated using a viscoelastic material model. Thereto, several parameters need to be determined. These consists of the time-independent instantaneous modulus, Prony series relaxation times and weights, and are reviewed in Section 3.1 and 3.2, respectively. The thermal dependency of the polymer is calibrated via a thermo-viscoelastic material model. Finally, the master curve and shift function need to be determined, which are discussed in Section 3.3 and 3.4, respectively. The approach outlined hereby provides a systematic approach to thermo-mechanical creep of polymers, which is generic in nature thus applicable to any thermoplastic materials.

3.1 The time-independent instantaneous modulus

The time-independent instantaneous modulus E^0 can be determined based on tensile yield measurements. These measurements are usually performed using ASTM D3039 tensile testing at a quasi-static strain rate. Note that the tensile and creep tests are performed at different time scales. The typical time scales for the tensile testing range in seconds, whereas the time scales for the creep testing range in hours. The experimental tensile stress-strain curves of the material can be imported in Digimat

– a material modelling software. Subsequently, an elastoplastic material model can be calibrated against the stress-strain curves of the material using an automatic calibration tool within the Digimat software. The time-independent instantaneous moduli E^0 can then be easily extracted.

3.2 Prony series relaxation terms, times and weights

The Prony series relaxation terms (see Section 2.2) can be determined based on tensile creep measurements. These measurements are performed using Zwick creep testing machine at a constant stress and the creep strain as a function of time is recorded. The tensile creep curves are fitted by a viscoelastic material model that is characterized by the sum of the Prony series weights. By re-arranging Equation (2), it can for instance be observed that the sum of the relaxation weights of the Prony series is given by:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{w}_i = \mathbf{1} - \frac{E^\infty}{E^0} \quad (4)$$

Hence, the sum of the weights of a Prony series equals a constant, which is dependent on the relaxation but independent on the number of terms considered in the Prony series. To be able to fit evolution of the creep, it is however recommended to have at least one Prony series term for each decade of the experimental measurements, such that the relaxation times of the Prony series are defined on a regular basis separated by ratios of ten.

The relaxation weights that are associated to the respective relaxation times are a measure of the stiffness variation around that relaxation time. For linear materials, the stiffness variation is computed using Hooke's law as the ratio of the applied stress to the respective creep strains:

$$E_i = \frac{\sigma}{\varepsilon_i} \quad (5)$$

Furthermore, a single relaxation of n -Prony series terms can be interpreted as n -incremental relaxations of a single Prony series term, see the schematic depiction in Figure 5. Thus, Equation (4) can be rewritten for each incremental relaxation as:

$$\sum_{i=1}^k \mathbf{w}_i = \mathbf{1} - \frac{E_k^\infty}{E^0} \quad (6)$$

Figure 5: A single relaxation of n -Prony series terms decomposed into n -incremental relaxations of a single Prony series term

Since these relaxations are incremental, the Prony series weights w_i can be computed by:

$$\mathbf{w}_i = \sum_{i=1}^k \mathbf{w}_i - \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \mathbf{w}_i \quad (7)$$

By using Equations (6) and (7), the Prony series weights w_i can further be expressed based on the time-independent tensile modulus E^0 and time-dependent creep moduli E^∞ as:

$$w_i = \frac{E_{k-1}^\infty - E_k^\infty}{E^0} \quad (8)$$

The approach outlined hereby provides a systematic approach to compute the weights of the Prony series relaxation terms in an unequivocal way, which is generic in nature thus applicable to any thermoplastic materials.

3.3 The construction of the master curve

The calibration of a thermo-viscoelastic material model requires a master curve (see Section 2.3) to be constructed at a reference temperature T_{ref} , *i.e.*, both the relaxation times and associated weights need to be established at T_{ref} . The time-temperature superposition principle is utilized to append the relaxation response measured at T to the master curve at T_{ref} (*e.g.*, see Figure 4).

In the further development (the details of which are given below), the master curve depicted in Figure 6 is constructed based on viscoelastic responses measured at temperatures T_{ref} and T , respectively, with $T_{ref} < T$ and in the range of relaxation times τ_i with $i = 1 \rightarrow n$. Since the time needed for a material to relax is higher at smaller temperature, the measurement at T is shifted to T_{ref} in the range of relaxation times τ_i with $i = n + 1 \rightarrow m$.

First, the relaxation times τ'_i of the master curve are computed. The relaxation times of the master curve consist of the relaxation times of the viscoelastic response at T_{ref} appended with the relaxation times of a viscoelastic response measured at T and shifted to T_{ref} . By the time-temperature superposition principle, the effect of lowering the temperature is equivalent to the effect of increasing the relaxation time of the viscoelastic response. Hence, to compute the relaxation times of a viscoelastic response measured at T and shifted to T_{ref} , the relaxation times are divided by the shift factor a_T given in Equation (3). Therefore, the relaxation times τ'_i of the master curve are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau'_i &= \tau_i & \text{for } i = 1 \rightarrow n \\ \tau'_i &= \frac{\tau_i}{a_T} & \text{for } i = n + 1 \rightarrow m \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Figure 6: A stress relaxation from T_{ref} to T

Next, the relaxation weights w'_i of the master curve are computed. The relaxation weights of the master curve consist of the relaxation weights of the viscoelastic response at T_{ref} appended with the relaxation weights of a viscoelastic response measured at T and shifted to T_{ref} . By the time-temperature

superposition principle, the effect of lowering the temperature is equivalent to the effect of lowering the strain rate of the viscoelastic response. Hence, to compute the weights of a viscoelastic response measured at T with respect to the time-independent instantaneous modulus measured at T_{ref} , an additional stress relaxation is considered which is schematically depicted in Figure 6. Therefore, the relaxation weights w'_i of the master curve are given by rewriting Equation (8) as:

$$\begin{aligned} w'_i &= w_i & \text{for } i = 1 \rightarrow n \\ w'_i &= \frac{E_{k-1}^T - E_k^T}{E_{ref}^T} & \text{for } i = n + 1 \rightarrow m \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Again, the approach outlined hereby provides a systematic approach to construct the master curve in an unequivocal way, which is generic in nature thus applicable to any thermoplastic materials.

3.4 The WLF shift function

To complete the thermo-mechanical creep calibration, the WLF shift function needs to be determined (see Section 2.3). The WLF parameters (C_1 and C_2) are linked to the horizontal shift factor α_T as given in Equation (3), which enables predictions for any temperature and over any time-scale (*e.g.*, see Figure 4). Since, a shift factor can be defined using measurements along the same time range at two constant temperatures (*e.g.*, see Figure 4), the measurements at three temperatures can be used to establish the two WLF parameters C_1 and C_2 via Equation (3).

4 APPLICATION CASE

Thermoplastic composites are increasingly used as load carrying materials and are replacing traditional materials. For example, thermoplastic composite pipes (TCPs) offer unique value propositions for metal dominated offshore oil & gas domain. The fully-bonded TCPs offered by Airborne Oil & Gas is enabling for deeper water exploration, production and intervention, and puts an end to corrosion. Creep response of thermoplastic material is an important design factor, which defines the design life of a product. The TCPs are subjected to various temperatures and loading conditions during their life. Thus, the characterization and predictability of the thermo-mechanical creep response is critical.

An application case study is discussed here for the thermoplastic composite consisting of high-density polyethylene (HDPE) reinforced with continuous glass-fibers. In Section 4.1, the material and available experimental data are outlined. The material is characterized experimentally by tensile and creep measurements at room (23 °C) and elevated (80 °C) temperatures. In Section 4.2, the necessary inputs of the viscoelastic material model calibration are reviewed, which includes the definition of the instantaneous moduli and Prony series. This forms the basis for the time-temperature superposition principle to be applied. In Section 4.3, the thermo-viscoelastic master curve is constructed, and the shift function is determined to predict the polymer response at another temperature (*e.g.*, 60 °C).

4.1 Material and experimental methods

HDPE is a widely used thermoplastic material for water and gas transport applications. It has a very high chemical resistance and is easy to process. Airborne Oil & Gas offers TCPs with cost effective materials, which are optimized for each application. For example, TCP consisting of HDPE reinforced with continuous glass-fibers is suitable for medium pressure (5 ksi) applications with the operating temperature up to 65 °C.

The quasi-static tensile response of the HDPE material is characterized using the ASTM D3039 standard test method at room (23°C) and elevated (80°C) temperatures. The stress-strain curves outline the thermo-mechanical response of the thermoplastic resin HDPE and are given in Figure 7. Note that at elevated temperature the material can undergo large deformations (*i.e.*, higher strain) at a relatively low stress value, see Figure 7.

Figure 7: Tensile stress-strain response of HDPE at 23 °C (blue) and 80 °C (red)

The creep response of the HDPE material is characterized using the Zwick creep testing machine, where the specimens were subjected to a constant stress of 5 MPa at 23 °C and 80 °C. The resulting creep curves are given in Figure 8. The thermo-mechanical creep response is clearly demonstrated, where creep is highly dependent on the temperature value, see Figure 8.

Figure 8: Tensile creep response of HDPE at 23 °C (blue) and 80 °C (red)

4.2 Viscoelastic calibrations

The viscoelastic material model is calibrated using an established material modelling software called Digimat. First, the elastoplastic material model is calibrated against the tensile stress-strain curves of the material (see Figure 7) using an automatic calibration tool within Digimat software. The calibrated thermo-mechanical material models are in good agreement with the experimental data at room (23°C) and elevated (80°C) temperatures, see Figure 9. Next, the time-independent instantaneous moduli (E^0) needed for the viscoelastic material model are extracted (see Section 3.1).

Figure 9: Tensile measurements (symbols) and calibrated elastoplastic models (solid lines) at 23 °C (blue) and 80 °C (red)

Finally, the Prony series relaxation times and associated weights are defined following the procedure described in Section 3.2. Number of Prony series terms have been considered at the different measurement intervals. Since the creep strains are recorded at a constant stress of 5 MPa, Hooke's law expressed in Equation (5) is used to compute the corresponding elastic moduli. Furthermore, Equation (8) is used to compute the relaxation weights w_i associated to the relaxation times of the Prony series. Note that the relaxation times τ_i correspond to the measurement's times. The results of this calibration approach are given in Figure 10 for both 23 °C and 80 °C.

Figure 10: Tensile creep measurements (symbols) and calibrated viscoelastic models (solid lines) at 23 °C (blue) and 80 °C (red)

4.3 Thermo-viscoelastic calibration

Calibration of the thermo-viscoelastic material model is carried out as per the procedure described in Section 3.3 and is based on the time-temperature superposition principle (see Section 2.3). First, the master curve is computed using the experimental data given in Figure 8. The reference temperature T_{ref} of the master curve has been defined at $T = 23 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Therefore, the viscoelastic relaxation at 80 °C needs to be shifted with respect to the time. The horizontal shift factor α_T is computed by re-arranging Equation (9) to:

$$\alpha_T = \frac{\tau_i}{\tau'_i} \quad (11)$$

As illustrated in Figure 11, a logarithmic extrapolation of the measurement at $T = 23 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is used to compute the horizontal shift factor α_T between the available measurements at 23 °C and 80 °C. The shift factor is then utilized to compute the Prony series relaxation times τ'_i and weights w'_i of the master curve using Equations (9) and (10), respectively.

Figure 11: Computation of the shift factor α_T

Next, the WLF parameters (C_1 and C_2 , see Section 2.3) are established to enable predictions for any temperature and over any time-scale. The WLF parameters are linked to the horizontal shift factor α_T as given in Equation (3). Here, we assume $C_2 = 57$, which is close to the values reported in the literature for the polymers. Thusly calibrated material model is then used to predict the creep response at an intermediate temperature $T = 60^\circ\text{C}$ and is given in Figure 12.

Figure 12: The thermo-viscoelastic model (solid lines) calibrated based on the tensile creep measurements (symbols) at 23°C (blue) and 80°C (red) predicts the creep response at 60°C (green)

Using Digimat software, the calibrated thermo-viscoelastic material model can further be used to predict the thermoplastic behavior at any loading condition in the linear viscoelasticity range. In Figure 13, the response is given for various temperatures and for two stress values, where the dashed and solid lines correspond to the lower and higher value of the stress, respectively.

Figure 13: The creep response at various temperatures (Blue: 23°C , Green: 60°C and Red: 80°C) and at two stress values, where the dashed and solid lines correspond to the lower and higher value of the stress, respectively. The symbols represent the experimental measurements

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Creep response of a material is an important design factor, which defines the design life of a product. Thus, characterization and predictability of the thermo-mechanical creep response is critical for the associated product design. The fully-bonded thermoplastic composite pipes (TCPs) offered by Airborne Oil & Gas consist of glass or carbon fibre reinforcements completely embedded within a thermoplastic material, *e.g.*, high-density polyethylene (HDPE), Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), etc. The TCPs are usually subjected to various temperatures and loading conditions during their design life.

The original contribution of the current study is towards establishing a generic framework to identify the creep calibration parameters unequivocally. The generic methodology developed herein can be used for any thermoplastic materials and provides a systematic, and time-efficient approach for the material calibration. An application case study is given for the thermoplastic composite consisting of HDPE reinforced with continuous glass-fibers. The creep response of the HDPE material is first calibrated for various temperatures and loading conditions using Digimat – a material modelling software. The thermo-mechanical creep response relies on the usual framework, *e.g.*, Prony series, master curve based on the time-temperature superposition, and Williams-Landel-Ferry shift function. Herewith, the calibrated thermo-viscoelastic material model enables to predict the viscoelastic relaxation at any temperature and over a wider range of time than would experimentally be possible.

A future step would be to use this model in a multi-scale approach implemented in Digimat to predict the behavior at the composite level. Composite would consist of the glass fibers and HDPE with defined fiber volume fraction. The glass fiber can be modelled as an elastic material for which the material parameters are usually well known. Thus, Digimat can easily be used to predict the composite response of HDPE reinforced with glass fibers. Note that the predictions will be based on a mean-field homogenization that combines the per-phase properties of the constituents (*e.g.*, matrix and fibers) with microstructural information (*e.g.*, fiber volume fraction) to generate the composite performance at the macroscopic scale.

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